

Types of prototypes

DRAWING

This is the most basic form of prototyping. Although it consists of simply drawing your idea, it will help you to define aspects that you had not thought of and to show in a simpler way parts of the idea that are difficult to verbalize.

This drawing is not intended to be a work of art. Keep in mind that **the content is important, not the form**. You can use different techniques to make it, from a pencil drawing to a collage.

Besides helping you to better define your idea, you can also use it to tell your solution to other people and receive feedback, thus having the opportunity to improve the idea.

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STORYBOARD

The storyboard is a **linear sequence of illustrations**, similar to a comic book, grouped together to form a story.

The key thing the storyboard gives us as a prototype is time. It allows you to show how your solution evolves in a sequence of steps. In addition, it also serves to show how the potential user of your solution interacts with the proposed idea. In the storyboard we can see **what happens before the idea is implemented, during and after**. Thanks to this technique, we get a much broader view of the solution and it helps us to understand it better.

It is important to keep in mind that this type of prototype is especially useful when the proposed solution is a service.

MOCKUP

A mock-up is a 3D representation of your idea. It consists of **building a physical model**, quickly and with affordable materials at hand or at low cost, such as cardboard and paper.

As in the other types of prototypes, the main focus is not on aesthetics, but on functionality. An advanced model of mock-up, easily accessible nowadays, is 3D printing. With this technique, more finished prototypes are achieved and ICTs are used in their construction.

Mock-ups are a very useful type of prototype when the solution devised consists of a product.

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ROLE PLAY

Role play is a **"theatrical" representation** of the solution devised. To do this, each member of the team is assigned a role to play, and this role is always a key part of the idea.

This type of prototype is very useful to deepen the development of service ideas, or to represent how the service works for other people.

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REPRESENTATION WITH OBJECTS

The role play with objects is an ideal variant of the role play when the project team consists of very few people or the role play is to be done with a single member.

Instead of acting out the idea with people, **the idea is acted out using objects**, such as dolls, toys or plasticine figures. A famous model of representation with objects in the world of Design Thinking is Lego Serious Play, where Lego figures are used to represent scenarios and solutions.

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